

REDUCED BOLTED JOINT MODEL USING MULTI-CONNECTED RIGID SURFACES AND CONTINUUM SHELL ELEMENTS

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Keywords: Bolted joints, Composite, Continuum shell element, Rigid Surfaces, Connector

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a reduced model of bolted joint using Multi-Connected Rigid Surfaces (MCRS) and continuum shell elements. The MCRS bolt model is constructed and identified from a numerical simulation of a single lap reference joint under tensile load, with the adherent parts and bolts represented by 3-D solid elements. The stiffness of the connector elements is determined, based on a physical approach, considering different deformation modes of bolt. The reduced joint model is then compared with the 3-D solid elements model in a 6-fastener configuration with large clearance value. The comparison covers overall response in terms of stiffness and load distribution between fasteners, local response in terms of stress fields and calculation times. Results show that the proposed model is able to drastically reduce calculation times while still providing a good estimate of the mechanical quantities needed for the study and dimensioning of multi-fastener joints.

1 INTRODUCTION

The design of fastened joints is based on making a good estimate of mechanical quantities as load distribution between fasteners and stress state near each fastener. These quantities are the result of a complex interaction between global behaviour of the joint and local behaviour at fastener scale.

The quantity and complexity of the phenomena involved lead us naturally to model the fastened joints using a refined mesh of 3-D solid elements. This type of model was developed in order to study the effect of the friction coefficient [1], clearance [2], location error [3] or tightening torque [4]. As well as predicting load distribution between the fasteners, these models also provide accurate results for the stress fields in the high gradient regions around the hole. They are also known for their ability to take material non-linearities into account, such as damage [2,5,6].

Setting up a model in order to reduce time calculation of multi-fastened joints and allowing an accurate estimation of both load distribution between fasteners and stress field around holes need keeping several physical phenomena. At structure scale, an analytical [3,7] or numerical [8,9] model representing fasteners with its equivalent stiffness could suffice to estimate load distribution. At material scale, modelling a local phenomenon as composite bearing damage need a higher precision local simulation. The complexity of behaviour of the material around fastener and non-linearity induced by contact conduce to take into account explicitly the 3-D geometry and the interaction between parts and fasteners. In the case of a tensile load applied on a single-lap joint, contact pressure field tends to change during loading due to secondary bending moment: localisation contact pressure in hole at overlap plane and under bolt head. Consequently a three-dimensional representation of contact surfaces and an implementation of a contact law are necessary in the reduced joint model if we want to capture that information.

A finite element model combining required phenomena for the estimation of both load distribution between fasteners and stress field at hole is proposed in this paper. The expected calculating time saving is the consequence of two reduction steps of a 3-D solid element model. The first step consists

in replacing solid 3-D elements of the bolt with rigid surfaces connected elastically. The construction and the validation of this model, noted MCRS (Multi-Connected Rigid Surfaces), is detailed in [10]. The second reduction of the model consists in using continuum shell elements for the joined parts. This type of elements has the advantage to possess solid 3-D geometry and shell behaviour. A three-dimensional contact between different surfaces is therefore insured. An eccentric tensile loading test applied on a 6-fastener single-lap joint is simulated with the proposed model in order to estimate the proposed model performances with multi-fastened joint and non-uniform bolt-load distribution. The comparison of several criteria shows the efficiency of the model to reproduce with a good precision both local and global behaviour of multi-fastened joints.

2 REDUCED BOLTED JOINT MODEL

2.1 Description of reference joint configuration

A single single-lap aluminium/composite joint with two bolts, as shown in Fig. 1, is considered as reference joint configuration in order to analyse bolt behaviour and extract equivalent stiffnesses for the reduced bolt model. The composite material is a carbon fibre laminate with unidirectional ply and a thermoset matrix IMA/M21. The stacking sequence for the composite adherent is $[90/-45/0/+45/0/-45/0/+45/90_{0.5}]_s$ and ply-thickness is 0.184 mm. The second adherent part assembled is made of aluminium alloy 7075. The two titanium bolts, diameter 6.35 mm, are fixed with an axial preload of 4800 N generating pressure under the head of about 62 MPa. All material properties are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1: Geometry of the reference joint.

Properties of unidirectional ply for T700GC/M21	E_{11} [GPa]	E_{22} [GPa]	E_{33} [GPa]			
	143	7.89	7.89			
	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{13} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
	3.92	3.92	2.76	0.33	0.33	0.43
Properties of aluminium alloy 7075	E [GPa]	ν				
	70	0.3				
Properties of titanium	E [GPa]	ν				
	110	0.3				

Table 1: Material properties used in reference model.

2.2 Description of 3-D reference model

A 3-D finite element model of the reference joint is created in Abaqus. All parts are meshed with 3-D solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R) as shown in Fig. 2.

Preload is modelled by initial penetration of 25 μm of each head into the adherent parts giving the aimed axial preload of 4800 N. A contact algorithm using the penalty method with a friction coefficient of 0.1 is also introduced to model contact between the bolts and the adherent parts. Equivalent stiffnesses are identified at a tensile load of about 15 kN, which corresponds to the initiation of bearing damage obtained experimentally.

Figure 2: Reference joint model: (a) Model mesh and boundary conditions, (b) Bolt model in reference model.

2.3 Bolt model description

The reduced bolt model is an assembly of rigid surfaces linked with 3-D connector elements. The choice to represent functional surfaces of fastener with 4 rigid surfaces is based on a preliminary analyse of deformation modes of a bolt fixed in the reference joint. This study showed that deformations in a fastener could be divided into three modes: axial, transverse and bending deformation modes. Every mode will be represented in the reduced bolt model by an equivalent stiffness in order to reproduce 3-D bolt behaviour. A connector noted C_0 linking the two pin surfaces PS_1 et PS_2 is integrated in order to represent axial stiffness K_{0_z} and transverse stiffnesses K_{0_x} et K_{0_y} of the bolt. Heads surfaces HS_1 and HS_2 are linked to pin surfaces through two other connectors C_1 and C_2 which represent transverse bending stiffnesses K_{1_x} and K_{1_y} (respectively K_{2_x} and K_{2_y}). The kinematic behaviour of the MCRS model is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Kinematic behaviour of reduced bolt model (MCRS).

2.4 Continuum shell model of adherents

Three-dimensional solid elements used for adherents in the reference model are replaced in the reduced model by continuum shell elements. A discretization with one 8-node shell element (SC8R) is realised in the thickness direction. This element allows introducing composite stacking sequence of plies by specifying for each one relative thickness and orientation. A classical homogenization of material properties resulting from laminated theory is thereafter integrated during calculation. As regards the out-of-plane behaviour, continuum shell elements include an out-of-plane stiffness and consequently make it possible to take into account pressure induced by the heads-adherent contact. This stiffness is defined assuming a constant normal stress σ_{zz} so that to respect continuity conditions at composite interfaces. This stress field is not directly accessible by the software.

2.5 Identification of the MCRS bolt model

The purpose of the connector elements introduced into the MCRS model is to transmit forces and moments and to position the rigid surfaces in the joint. The external actions applied by adherents and the relative displacements of heads-adherents contact surfaces Ω_1 and Ω_2 of one bolt given by the reference model as shown in Fig. 4 are used for the determination of axial stiffness K_{0_z} and angular stiffnesses $K_{1_x}, K_{1_y}, K_{2_x}$ and K_{2_y} [10]. The displacement of Ω_1 (respectively Ω_2) is defined by column vector of small displacement $[D_1]$ (respectively $[D_2]$). The components (u_x, u_z, θ_y) of these vectors represent the relative motion in the load plane (XZ) of the centre of a flat disc constructed from nodes of Ω_1 or Ω_2 by least-squares method.

Forces and moments in (XZ) plane are grouped in two other column vectors $[T_1]$ and $[T_2]$. Displacements and external actions are expressed in a local coordinate system of the pin $(\vec{x}, \vec{y}, \vec{z})$ centred on O (O being the intersection of the bolt axis in its deformed state and the overlap plane of the joint):

$$\Omega_1 : [D_1] = \begin{bmatrix} u_{x_1} \\ u_{z_1} \\ \theta_{y_1} \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } [T_1] = \begin{bmatrix} F_{x_1} \\ F_{z_1} \\ M_{y_1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\Omega_2 : [D_2] = \begin{bmatrix} u_{x_2} \\ u_{z_2} \\ \theta_{y_2} \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } [T_2] = \begin{bmatrix} F_{x_2} \\ F_{z_2} \\ M_{y_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

For the axial stiffness K_{0_z} , the displacement cumulates for the most part in the bolt head. The representative force transmitted by the connector C_0 is defined as the mean of axial forces F_{z_1} and F_{z_2} . Angular stiffnesses K_{1_x} , K_{1_y} , K_{2_x} et K_{2_y} are calculated from the ratio between moments and rotational angles.

$$K_{0_z} = \frac{1}{2} \left| \frac{F_{z_1} + F_{z_2}}{u_{z_1} + u_{z_2}} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$K_{1_x} = K_{1_y} = \left| \frac{M_{y_1}}{\theta_{y_1}} \right| \quad (4)$$

$$K_{2_x} = K_{2_y} = \left| \frac{M_{y_2}}{\theta_{y_2}} \right| \quad (5)$$

Figure 4: Definition of surfaces Ω_1 et Ω_2 of the reference model.

The method we propose here to determine shear/bearing-compression stiffness K_{0_x} and K_{0_y} is based on an energy approach, given the difficulty in estimating equivalent displacements and forces applied on the functional surfaces modelling the pin in the same way as the transverse rotational and translational along \vec{z} stiffnesses.

As only stiffness $K_{0_x} = K_{0_y}$ has not yet been identified, we search for the value of this stiffness that will equal the strain energy of the bolt calculated with the 3-D reference model and the sum of the strain energies for all the connectors in the MCRC model. The value chosen for K_{0_x} is deduced from the intersection of the graph representing the change in strain energy estimated with the MCRC model and the level of strain energy calculated with the 3-D reference model at a load of 15 kN. Note that at

this load level, the strain energy associated with transverse stiffness K_{0_x} represents about 80% of the total strain energy of the bolt, thus making this a reliable method of identification. Stiffnesses identified for each connector are listed in Table 2.

Connector	C_0			C_1		C_2	
Stiffness	K_{0_x} [kN/mm]	K_{0_y} [kN/mm]	K_{0_z} [kN/mm]	K_{1_x} [kN.mm]	K_{1_y} [kN.mm]	K_{2_x} [kN.mm]	K_{2_y} [kN.mm]
	260	260	118	2025	2025	1998	1998

Table 2: Connectors and associated stiffnesses

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Validation case description

The multi-bolt joint taken on to evaluate reduced model efficiency are a 3-row, 2-column bolted joint as shown in Fig .5. The six bolts are fixed with radial clearance of 125 μm . A tensile load offset from symmetry plane of 10 mm is applied on the composite adherent, as shown in Fig. 6, in order to create a non-uniform load distribution between fasteners and to have contact force directions deviated from x-axis.

Figure 5: Multi-bolt joint geometry.

Figure 6: Mesh and boundary conditions of the multi-bolt joint.

3.2 Load distribution

A total displacement of 1 mm is applied on the assembly. Load-displacement curves shown in Fig. 7 are determined from contact forces: both normal and tangential contact forces are taken into account. The comparison of bolt-load curves shows that MCRS model gives an accurate response. The similarity of bolt-load curves shows globally a correct modelling of the bolt-adherent contact and an accurate estimation of equivalent bolt stiffnesses. The gap about 30% of the tangential friction load, as illustrated in Fig .8a, is essentially due to an underestimation of the axial bolt stiffnesses. However, at a high load, the (Fig .8b) shows a reduction of the gap between bolt-loads given by MCRS and 3-D models (less than 1%).

Figure 7: Load-displacement curves transmitted by each bolt of the joint.

Figure 8: Comparison of bolt-load distribution: (a) During sliding step (joint displacement of 0.2 mm), (b) At higher level of load (joint displacement of 0.7 mm).

3.3 Stress field around holes

The strength of the assembled parts is based on the distribution and amplitude of the stresses around the hole. Only the results for the composite adherent part are shown here. For composite materials, the model should correctly predict stress in the direction of the fibres under tension (failure initiation in net-section) and under compression (bearing damage initiation). Note that many studies [11–13] have shown that the failure of fibres under compression loading also depends on shear stresses and transverse stresses. This fields could be used to calculate a failure criteria [14] or associated to a damage model [5,15]. Therefore, in order to assess the efficiency of the MCRS model at the scale of the material, it is vital to compare the field of the in-plane components of the stress tensor (Fig. 9) at the edge of the hole in the ply coordinate system: direction 1 is the direction of the fibres and direction 2 is transverse direction in the lay-up plane.

The comparison is made between the 3-D and MCRS models at the edge of the hole in the composite adherent part in contact with bolt 4. Stress fields are extracted at a bolt-load of 13 kN. Results obtained on the other holes are similar. The comparison of the in-plane stress fields shows a similar distribution. The localisation of the stresses observed at the overlap plane shows an accurate estimation of contact pressure and a correct simulation of the kinematic of the MCRS surfaces. However the gap for some ply could be important. It is the case of the 90° ply near the overlap plane. The 3-D model shows that contact surface not remains cylindrical because of some plies, which are less stiff, are more deformed generating an out-of-plane shear stress. This phenomenon couldn't obviously been captured by shell elements.

Figure 9: Comparison of stress fields at the edge of the hole in the composite adherent part in contact with bolt 4 for a bolt-load of 13 kN.

3.4 Calculation time

Numerical simulations of the different models were carried out with an Abaqus implicit scheme using 4 cores of an Intel Xeon 16-cores 2 GHz processor and 64 GB RAM computer. With the 6-fastener MCRS joint model there is a total calculation time saving of about 93% compared with the 3-D bolt model. Reducing the number of degrees of freedom by using rigid analytical surfaces means that not only the size of the stiffness matrix of the FE model can be reduced but also the number of degrees of freedom involved in the contact algorithm. However, this last point may have a negative effect since by making the bolt rigid, resolving the contact law may become more difficult.

4 CONCLUSION

This article proposes a model of multi-fastened joint using rigid surfaces connected elastically representing the fastener and continuum shell element for the adherents. The construction of the bolt model (MCRS) is based on a reference finite element model made up entirely of solid 3-D elements. The combination of rigid surfaces and continuum shell elements insure a 3-D contact. This allows explicitly the inclusion in the model of the effect of clearance, preload and friction coefficient. The model is tested with a 6-fastener single-lap configuration. Results showed an accurate load distribution between fasteners and satisfactory stress fields while saving about 93% of calculation time.

In addition, the fact that the true shape of the parts is explicitly represented with the holes means that failure criteria or non-linear laws resulting from plasticity or damage at the material scale can be applied directly, thus avoiding a stage of local re-analysis or the use of macroscopic criteria within a narrow validity domain.

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